

QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF DENTAL SERVICES BY PATIENTS IN GERMANY

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ABSTRACT

In recent years there has been a rise in patients' expectations and requirements regarding the quality of dental care. This is the result of the continuously increasing competition in the health services market, respectively within dental practices. This article studies and analyses the factors which form the quality assessment of dental services by patients in Germany. These include the frequency for visiting a dental office, the access to the practice, its organisation and the waiting times. What has also been analysed is the quality of dental services received and the dental procedures for which patients most often make co-payments in Germany.

Keywords: quality, dental services, patients.

The patient-centered model has transformed the patient from a passive participant in the diagnostic and treatment process into an active figure with his/her own value system, understandings, knowledge and perspective, that take a central place in the decisions regarding his/her health [5].

Patients choose to visit a certain dental office, which will satisfy their needs to the highest degree of their expectations [3]. The dental service quality has a leading role in this choice. Since patients' knowledge in this area is limited, they can objectively evaluate only to a certain extent the treatment they have received. There has been a rise in patients' expectations and requirements regarding the quality of dental care. This is the result of the continuously increasing competition in the health services market, respectively within dental practices. This necessitates that dental practice managers constantly study, analyse and show interest in the factors impacting patient satisfaction and the methods and means for optimizing the quality of dental service. Good treatment outcomes and the high quality of the dental service are no longer sufficient for ensuring a long-term success of a dental practice on their own [4]. The service in the dental office is much more than simply providing a health care. As the patients have turned into clients for the health services, there has been a rising need for them to take on an active role in the decision-making regarding their own oral health. The communication with the patient, the manner in which the information is provided, and the respect for the patient's opinion during the course of treatment, have taken a crucial role in the positive assessment of the provided dental services.

The aim of the present study is to make a comprehensive analysis of the factors that shape the assessment of the quality of dental services by patients in Germany.

To achieve the goal of the study, we set the following tasks:

1. Analyse the frequency and reason for visiting a dental practice in Germany.

2. Study and analyse the access, organization and waiting times in the dental practice.

3. Analyse the quality of the received dental services, according to the respondents.

4. Study the direct co-payments for dental services received in German dental practices.

5. Formulate conclusions from the conducted research

Methodology A questionnaire survey method was used to collect the data for this article. 200 patients residing in the city of Schifferstadt, Germany responded to the questionnaire. They were all above 18 years of age, and the principles of voluntarily participation and anonymity were upheld. The survey was carried out in the span of 2 months (from 01.03.2023 to 30.04.2023). The questionnaire contained 26 questions and was carried out after the patients had undergone examinations and consultations with dental physicians, which indicates that the results are reliable.

Statistical methods - descriptive statistics - were used to process the information obtained from the survey. The specialised statistics package SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) 20.0 was used to process the survey data.

Results and discussion:

An anonymous questionnaire survey was conducted among 200 patients of dental clinics in the city of Schifferstadt, Germany in order to analyse the factors which influence the patients' satisfaction with the received dental services and their evaluation of those services. The respondents comprised of 108 men (54%) and 92 women (46%).

The analysis of the questionnaire data shows that 52% of the surveyed patients in Germany visit their dentist for preventive purposes more than once a year. 32% of the respondents visit the dentist's office once a year, and 16% of the patients surveyed only in case they have a particular complaint (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Frequency and reasons for dental office visits

One of the reasons for this result is that according to 96.97% of the respondents regular preventive check-ups and treatments are essential for the prevention and early diagnosis of oral cavity diseases. Another reason is the high level of patients' health literacy in Germany who visit their dentist at least once per year for a tartar

removal (a preventive dental service, fully covered by the National Health Services) or a professional teeth cleaning.

Figure 2 presents the results related to the time patients had to wait for an appointment in the dental office.

Figure 2 Waiting time for a dental appointment as a factor influencing the quality assessment of dental services

The largest percentage of the respondents had to wait more than one calendar week for their appointment (40%), while 30% of the participants received a dentist appointment within a calendar week, only because they had a complaint, and the remaining 30% of the patients received an appointment within one calendar week.

Another factor that had a leading role in shaping the patients' quality assessment of the received dental

services is the time spent in the waiting room (Figure 3) [1]. Only 11% of the participants had an immediate appointment for a check-up or a treatment without any waiting time. For the majority of the patients - 76%, the waiting time was less than 30 minutes and 13% of the patients waited for more than 30 minutes.

Figure 3: Estimation of waiting time in dental practices

The technical equipment of the dental practices, the professional competence of the dentist and the quality of the received dental services are also some of the leading factors in the patients' positive assessment of the dental care quality. Here, too, extremely high levels

of satisfaction were observed among the respondents. 74,5% of the patients surveyed were satisfied with the technical equipment of the dental office, while as many as 20% responded with "unable to assess" (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Assessment of the technical equipment of the dental practice

The reason for this could be that the patients do not have a professional knowledge related to the materials, technologies and methods in dentistry. In most cases, as long-term patients, they also lack basis for comparison when it comes to the equipment available in other dental offices [2]. According to the author of this article, it is the duty and responsibility of the dentist and the dental team to inform their patients on the new technologies, tools and equipment used in the dental

practice. Particularly as in most cases their use in the course of treatment, requires co-payment by the patient (e.g. apex locator, endodontic motor, laser, etc.)

99% of respondents would recommend their dentist to family and friends, a testament to the high levels of satisfaction with the received dental services.

The dental services for which patients in Germany most frequently paid a co-payment are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Dental services for which patients in Germany paid a co-payment most frequently

The highest percentage of co-payments was for professional dental cleaning - 66%. Unlike tartar removal, which aims to remove only the tartar visible on the tooth surface (supragingival), professional teeth cleaning is a thorough cleaning and removal of dental deposits, plaque and biofilm, both on visible tooth surfaces and in hard-to-reach areas such as periodontal pockets. More than half of the respondents indicated that they have made a co-payment for fillings made of aesthetic composite material in the invisible part of the dentition, since health insurance companies only cover the costs for amalgam fillings. A relatively large number of patients - 37% made co-payments for prosthetic constructions, 13% - for implants, and 11% of the surveyed patients have not paid extra for dental services.

We can draw the following conclusions from the presented analysis of the questionnaire survey results:

1. More than half of the surveyed patients (52%) visit the dental practice more than once a year only for preventive purposes i.e. without symptoms present.
2. 96.97% of the surveyed patients consider regular preventive check-ups and tartar removal to be crucial to the prevention and early diagnosis of oral cavity diseases.
3. A large proportion of respondents (40%) had to wait more than one calendar week to receive an appointment for an examination or a treatment.
4. Only 11% of the surveyed patients indicated that they did not have to wait at the dental practice, while for 76% of patients the waiting time was up to 30 minutes.

5. Despite the high health insurance contributions and the wide range of dental procedures covered by the national health insurance companies, co-payments by patients are relatively common. Most often patients have made co-payments for professional teeth cleaning (preventive dental service) and for aesthetic composite fillings in the invisible part of the dentition.

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